

Flux Spectra Variation due to Insertion of Target Pebbles for Covert Material Production in Pebble-Bed Reactors

Annie Berens^{1,*}, Tomi Akindele¹, Tyana Stiegler¹, Sandra Bogetic²

¹Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, 7000 East Ave., Livermore, CA;

²University of Tennessee - Knoxville, 863 Neyland Dr., Knoxville, TN

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.20804054

ABSTRACT

Pebble-bed reactors (PBRs) are increasingly being considered by countries and private companies for deployment for applications such as driving chemical processes or powering data centers. PBRs differ largely from conventional light-water reactors (LWRs) and therefore challenge exiting International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) safeguards verification measures, especially in regards to maintaining, and regaining, continuity of knowledge during operation. Previous applications of IAEA safeguards to a PBR facility identified several credible diversion pathways. A covert misuse scenario, based on these pathways, involved the insertion of target pebbles into the reactor core to produce weapons-usable material. Two different natural uranium-bearing target pebble designs were considered, one that matched the weight of a conventional fuel pebble and another that maximized the natural uranium volume. This work assessed the impact of the insertion of target pebbles for covert material production on the flux spectrum and flux profile in an equilibrium PBR core. In comparing the misuse models, containing the target pebbles, to the baseline model, differences in the flux spectra and axial flux profiles only occurred in the lower regions of the core. At the reactor bottom, relative differences of up to 6% in the thermal peak of the flux spectrum when comparing the misuse models to the baseline model.

Keywords: Safeguards, Pebble-Bed Reactors

1. INTRODUCTION

Pebble-bed reactors (PBRs) are an advanced reactor design that are increasingly being considered in the U.S. and internationally for power production for a variety of applications, including chemical processing and data centers. Compared to conventionally operated and deployed light water reactors (LWRs), PBRs utilize higher enrichment fuel, online refueling and pebble-type fuel, all of which will challenge existing International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) safeguards verification measures [1]. The first PBRs were designed by the Research Center Jülich and operated in Germany, beginning in 1966 with the Arbeitsgemeinschaft Versuchsreaktor, a research reactor, and followed by the commercial Thorium High-Temperature Reactor in 1983 [2]. Leveraging lessons learned in the construction and operation of the German PBRs, the Institute for Nuclear and New Energy Technology (INET) at Tsinghua University designed the 10 MWth High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor (HTR-1) that began operating in 2000 [3]. Utilizing information attained during the operation of the HTR-10, the commercial High-Temperature Pebble-Bed Reactor Module (HTR-PM) was designed at INET and began operation in 2021 [1].

1.1. Existing IAEA Safeguards Applications

In 2017, five years into its construction, the HTR-PM was added to the list of eligible facilities in China under the Voluntary Offer Agreement (VOA) [1]. The HTR-PM was selected by the IAEA for the application of safeguards in order to learn and gain experience with a PBR design that may be, in the future,

*berens1@llnl.gov

exported to Non-Nuclear Weapons States (NNWS) [1]. The IAEA, working in coordination with INET, the HTR-PM operators and the Chinese Atomic Energy Agency, identified possible safeguards measures, including the installation of IAEA safeguards monitoring equipment, to address the safeguards challenges in the HTR-PM. Three main technical objectives were identified based upon credible diversion pathways [1]: (1) Detect diversion of fresh fuel containers or pebbles with or without substitution by dummy spheres prior to loading, (2) Detect diversion of core fuels or irradiated target materials with or without substitution by dummy fuels or falsification of operating records, and (3) Detect diversion of spent fuel pebbles with or without substitution by dummy fuels.

Based upon the technical objectives, the fresh fuel loading and storage area, reactor containment building and the spent fuel storage area were identified as three key measurement points for the application of safeguards [1]. After operation of the HTR-PM begins, the reactor containment building, which contains the two reactor cores and the shared steam generator, is considered inaccessible for the entirety of the HTR-PM's operation. Continuity of knowledge is maintained through surveillance of fresh fuel pebbles being loaded into the reactor containment building, and through surveillance and non-destructive analysis (NDA) at key penetration areas where irradiated fuel pebbles could be removed [1]. However, due to the inaccessibility of the reactor containment building there are no technical means of recovering continuity of knowledge if the applied containment and surveillance measures fail. It is proposed that operational data of the material circulating through the reactor would be available "on-line" to the IAEA so that if containment and surveillance fail continuity of knowledge can be recovered. This "on-line" material monitoring would be provided through the dual-use of the burnup monitoring system (BUMS) [1]. However, the BUMS does not have any in-core monitoring capabilities, instead providing operation information based on pebbles that have exited the core.

2. SCOPE OF THIS WORK

This work assessed the impact of the insertion of target pebbles for covert material production on the flux spectrum and flux profile in the core of a PBR operating at equilibrium. The paper first identifies potential misuse scenarios, followed by a description of the computational methods used to quantify changes in flux spectra and profiles resulting from these scenarios. Overall, this work supports current efforts of determining additional monitoring methods for PBRs to ensure continuity of knowledge in the reactor containment building during operation.

3. METHODOLOGY

The misuse scenario that was being assessed as part of this work was the covert insertion of target pebbles into a PBR core for the purpose of the production of weapons usable material. This scenario corresponds to the second credible diversion pathway identified by the IAEA for the HTR-PM [1]. Two types of target pebbles were modeled, with specifications summarized in Table I. All pebbles had an outer diameter of 60 mm and outer coating thickness of 5 mm. The case 1 pebble, shown in Figure 1, has a thin layer of natural uranium that is surrounded by an outer graphite coating. This target pebble was designed such that the weight of a target pebble is equal to the weight of a conventional pebble, so that the target pebbles would not be identified in any cask weight verification scenario. The case 2 target pebble (Figure 2) utilizes a solid natural uranium core that is surrounded by an outer graphite coating. The insertion of target pebbles into the reactor core leads to a reduction in the reactivity, as the natural uranium primarily absorbs neutrons. As the misuse scenario being assessed is a covert one, no changes to the operation of the reactor were considered. Therefore, target pebble insertion was only allowable utilizing the excess reactivity of the PBR at equilibrium. Generally, PBRs are designed to be operated at equilibrium with minimal excess reactivity for safety purposes, severely limiting the number of target pebbles that can be inserted into the core.

In order to analyze this covert misuse scenario, a model of a generic pebble-bed high-temperature gas-

Table I. Relevant pebble design specifications for the different target pebble designs used in the gPB-HTGR.

	Conventional [4]	Case 1	Case 2
Enrichment	15.5%	Natural Uranium	Natural Uranium
Pebble Mass	203.45 g	203.45 g	1,237.00 g
Natural Uranium Inner Diameter	-	48.32 mm	-

Figure 1. Case 1 target pebble which utilizes a thin natural uranium lining on the carbon outer coating for plutonium production.

Figure 2. Case 2 target pebble that utilizes a solid natural uranium center for plutonium production.

cooled reactor (gPB-HTGR) at equilibrium was used, based upon publicly available specifications of the 165 MWth Xe-100 [4]. Berens et al. [5] utilized the SCALE Leap-In method for Cores at Equilibrium (SLICE) to develop this equilibrium model [6]. A PBR is considered to be operating at equilibrium when the regional nuclide inventory no longer changes over time regardless of the insertion or removal of pebbles from the core. SCALE is modeling and simulation suite comprised of a system of integrated modules with a variety of applications, including reactor physics [7]. In this work, the SCALE module TRITON was used. TRITON couples Monte Carlo (MC) transport, utilizing KENO-VI, with depletion, utilizing the depletion and decay solver ORIGEN. The FULCRUM graphical user interface was also used for 3D visualization of the core and analysis of the local flux spectra. For this work, the original equilibrium model developed by Berens et al. was adjusted to include both radial and axial discretization. Each axial zone in the reactor was discretized into four radial zones of equal volume. The axial discretization of the gPB-HTGR is shown in Figure 3. While each of the radial zones in an axial zone do contain the same fuel inventory, the discretization allows for some radial variation in flux to be captured.

Figure 3. Axial discretization of the gPB-HTGR into 10 axial zones.

The first step towards understanding the flux spectra variation due to the above mentioned covert misuse scenario was determining the maximum insertion of target pebbles into the reactor core for each target pebble case. Within the gPB-HTGR equilibrium model, the percentage of conventional fuel pebbles being replaced by target pebbles was incrementally increased until the k_{eff} value from the TRITON calculation became subcritical. The locations of the conventional pebbles being replaced by target pebbles was random within each axial zone. Once the maximum target pebble insertion was determined for each target pebble case, a mesh was added into the TRITON model. The geometric characteristics of this mesh were determined by considering the physics of a PBR and the end-use of the information generated in this work. Fundamental to the theory of equilibrium in a PBRs is the fact that in a PBR, the flux spectrum experienced by a singular pebble is driven by the isotopic composition of the neighboring pebbles, instead of the singular pebble itself. This is due to the long path length of neutrons in graphite. Therefore, the application of a fine mesh to the model to determine local flux differences surrounding the individual target pebbles does not yield overly meaningful results. Instead the flux mesh was applied such that a cell of the mesh covered the entire axial zone, capturing the combined effect of the target pebbles. This meshing decision also reflected the potential application of this work in determining the logistics of a flux monitoring system in the reflector surrounding the reactor core. For such flux detection system, radially discretized flux information would be minimally important as this resolution would be challenging to attain.

4. RESULTS

As described in Section 3, in the covert misuse scenario being assessed in this work the percentage of conventional pebbles that can be replaced by target pebbles is directly dependent on the available excess reactivity in the core at equilibrium. Figure 4 shows the change in reactivity in the gPB-HTGR with an increasing percent insertion of case 1 and case 2 target pebbles. For the case 1 target pebble, a maximum of 1.2% of the conventional pebbles in the reactor core could be replaced with target pebbles while maintaining criticality. Due to the higher U-238 volume in the case 2 target pebbles, a maximum of only 0.25% of the conventional pebbles in the core could be replaced with target pebbles.

Figure 5 shows the flux spectra of the baseline model compared to the two misuse models in axial zone 1, 3, 7 and 10 in the reactor. Towards the bottom of the reactor, i.e. in axial zones 7 and 10, the relative differences between the baseline and misuse models become more pronounced. In axial zone 10, the thermal peak of the model utilizing case 1 target pebbles was 5.2% lower than that of the baseline model.

Figure 4. Change in k_{eff} value, with statistical error from MC calculation, of the gPB-HTGR with increasing percent insertion of case 1 and case 2 target pebbles.

Similarly, there was a 5.9% decrease in the thermal flux peak for the model utilizing case 2 target pebbles compared to the baseline model. Additionally, there is also a slight decrease in the flux in the resonance and fast regions for the misuse models compared to the baseline. The depression of the flux in the misuse models compared to the baseline is due to neutron capture occurring in the U-238 in the target pebbles. The U-238 neutron capture cross-section is largest in the resonance range, thereby reducing the number of neutrons that are thermalized. The relative reduction in flux is less pronounced near the top of the reactor, in axial zones 1 and 3, because the magnitude of the flux in these zones is higher. Consequently, the relative reduction in the thermal flux peak is greater than in the lower axial zones where the flux magnitude is lower.

This reduction in thermal flux can also be seen when comparing the normalized thermal flux profiles of the misuse models to the baseline model. Shown in Figure 6 are the normalized axial thermal flux profiles for the four radial zones in the gPB-HTGR. In the upper regions of the core there is a high level of agreement between the baseline and misuse models. Deviation in the thermal flux only begins to occur in the lower region of the core, where the thermal flux magnitude of misuse models drop below that of the baseline model, consistent with the behavior seen in Figure 5. These axial fast flux profiles across the radial zones are shown in Figure 7. Reflective of the behavior seen in Figure 5, deviation in the fast flux from the baseline primarily occurred in the lower region of the core, although the deviation was minimal compared to that of the thermal flux.

Based on the discussed results, it is possible to determine that any form of flux monitoring system that would be placed within the reactor containment building should be positioned near the bottom of the core. For the covert misuse scenario being assessed in this work, there is no discernible signature of misuse in the flux spectra in the upper part of the core. While the neutron capture on the U-238 in the target pebbles is reducing the neutron economy, the conventional pebbles, which vastly outnumber the target pebbles, have sufficient fissile material such relative difference in the flux spectra is minimal. Towards the bottom of the core, the average conventional pebble burnup increases, leading to a corresponding decrease in the flux due to the decreasing amount of fissile U-235. Based on the baseline model, this behavior is expected in PBRs operating at equilibrium. However, for the misuse models the relative reduction in flux, particularly the thermal flux, is larger in the lower region of the core as the reduced

Figure 5. Flux spectra in axial zones 1, 3, 7 and 10 in the gPB-HTGR for the baseline and misuse models.

fissile material means that the magnitude of the flux is lower in these zones. It is in these lower flux regions at the bottom of the core that relative differences of up to 6% were seen in the thermal peak of the flux spectrum. Therefore, placing a flux monitoring system in the lower region of the core could enable the detection of the discussed covert misuse scenario.

Figure 6. Normalized axial thermal flux profiles of the baseline and misuse models for the four radial zones.

Figure 7. Normalized axial thermal flux profiles of the baseline and misuse models for the four radial zones.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This work sought to assess the impact of the inclusion of target pebbles, for the purpose of covert material production, on the flux spectrum and flux profile within a PBR. The covert misuse scenario being analyzed was the use of natural uranium target pebbles in a PBR for clandestine production of plutonium. Two different pebble designs were considered. The case 1 design maintained the same mass as a conventional pebble through the use of a thin natural uranium lining and the case 2 pebble design utilized a natural uranium core surrounded by a graphite outer coating. Models were first developed of the gPB-HTGR with different percentages of the conventional pebbles being replaced by either case 1 or case 2 target pebbles. The maximum replacement was determined to be 1.2% with the case 1 target pebbles and 0.25% with the case 2 target pebbles. Using the models that contained the maximum percentage of the case 1 and case 2 target pebbles, a flux mesh was added to the TRITON model to look at the axially dependent flux spectrum. It was found that in the upper region of the gPB-HTGR there was no discernible difference between the flux spectrum in the baseline model and in the two misuse models. However, near the bottom of the core relative differences in the thermal flux peak of up to 6% were found. Similar behavior was found when analyzing the flux profiles in the reactor, with thermal and fast flux differences primarily occurring the the lower axial zones. For future work in developing an in reactor flux monitoring system to detect this type of covert misuse, such system should be placed towards the bottom of the reactor where discernible flux differences between the baseline and misuse models could be detected.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was performed under the auspices of the U.S. Department of Energy by Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory under contract DE-AC52-07NA27344. This research was funded through LLNL's Laboratory Directed Research and Development Program. LLNL-CONF-2013082.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Becker, A. Rialhe, J. Whitlock, and J. Doo. "IMPLEMENTATION OF SAFEGUARDS MEASURES AT THE HIGH TEMPERATURE GAS-COOLED REACTOR PEBBLE-BED MODULE (HTR-PM) IN CHINA AND PROPOSED SAFEGUARDS BY DESIGN FOR UNITS TO BE EXPORTED TO OTHER STATES."
- [2] K. Krüger, G. Ivens, and N. Kirch. "Operational experience and safety experiments with the AVR power station." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 109**(1-2), pp. 233–238 (1988). Publisher: Elsevier.
- [3] D. She, F. Chen, B. Xia, and L. Shi. "Simulation of the HTR-10 operation history with the PANGU code." *Frontiers in Energy Research*, **volume 9**, p. 704116 (2021). Publisher: Frontiers Media SA.
- [4] E. J. Mulder and W. A. Boyes. "Neutronics characteristics of a 165MWth Xe-100 reactor." *Nuclear Engineering and Design*, **volume 357**, p. 110415 (2020). URL <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0029549319304467>.
- [5] A. Berens, F. Bostelmann, and N. R. Brown. "Equilibrium core modeling of a pebble bed reactor similar to the Xe-100 with SCALE." *Progress in Nuclear Energy*, **volume 171**, p. 105187 (2024).
- [6] F. Bostelmann, S. E. Skutnik, and W. Wieselquist. "Introducing the SLICE Method for Estimating Pebble-Bed Reactor Inventories at Equilibrium Operation with SCALE." *Annals of Nuclear Energy* (2025).
- [7] W. A. Wieselquist and R. A. Lefebvre Eds. "SCALE 6.3.1 User Manual." Technical Report ORNL/TM-SCALE-6.3.1, UT-Battelle, LLC, Oak Ridge National Laboratory, Oak Ridge, TN (2023).